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THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DURING THE REIGN OF MIRZO ULUG'BEK

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Abstract: The article describes the development of entrepreneurship during the time of Mirzo Ulugbek and its role in state policy. Although Ulugbek himself was not an entrepreneur, it is noted that he created favorable conditions for merchants and artisans. A reasonable tax system and free trade relations served economic development. Also, the construction of caravanserais, madrasahs, markets and other public facilities developed the infrastructure of the city. As a result, during Ulugbek's time, architecture, crafts, trade and science developed at a high level.

Key words: Mirzo Ulugbek, entrepreneurship, trade, crafts, architecture, infrastructure, caravanserai, tax system, science.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Mirzo Ulug'bek davrida tadbirkorlikning rivoji va uning davlat siyosatida tutgan o'rni yoritilgan. Ulug'bekning o'zi tadbirkor bo'lmagan bo'lsa-da, savdogarlar va hunarmandlar uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratgani ta'kidlanadi. Oqilona soliq tizimi va erkin savdo munosabatlari iqtisodiy taraqqiyotga xizmat qilgan. Shuningdek, karvonsaroylar, madrasalar, bozorlar va boshqa jamoat inshootlari qurilishi shahar infratuzilmasini rivojlantirgan. Natijada, Ulug'bek davrida me'morchilik, hunarmandchilik, savdo va ilm-fan yuksak darajada ravnaq topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mirzo Ulug'bek, tadbirkorlik, savdo-sotiq, hunarmandchilik, me'morchilik, infratuzilma, karvonsaroy, soliq tizimi, ilm-fan.

Аннотация: В статье описывается развитие предпринимательства во времена Мирзо Улугбека и его роль в государственной политике. Хотя сам Улугбек не был предпринимателем, отмечается, что он создал благоприятные условия для торговцев и ремесленников. Разумная налоговая система и свободные торговые отношения способствовали экономическому развитию. Также строительство караван-сараяв, медресе, рынков и других общественных сооружений способствовало развитию городской инфраструктуры. В результате, во времена Улугбека архитектура, ремесла, торговля и наука достигли высокого уровня развития.

Ключевые слова: Мирзо Улугбек, предпринимательство, торговля, ремесла, архитектура, инфраструктура, караван-сарай, налоговая система, наука.

INTRODUCTION

The Timurid period, particularly the years of Mirzo Ulug'bek's rule, is characterized in the history of Central Asia by a remarkable rise in science, culture, and economic life. Although Ulug'bek is best known as an astronomer and mathematician, his economic policies in state governance contributed significantly to the development of entrepreneurial activity in the country. The purpose of this article is to provide a scholarly analysis of the formation of the entrepreneurial environment during the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek and to identify its main contributing factors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The Timurid period, especially the years of Mirzo Ulug'bek's rule, occupies a distinctive place in the history of Central Asia not only due to advances in science and culture, but also because of the development of economic life and entrepreneurial relations. In analyzing the economic processes of this period, the studies of A. Abdullaev on the history of the Timurid era serve as an important source. In his works, the author extensively examines state governance, financial policy, and the conditions created for the stable functioning of the economic system, while also analyzing the factors that contributed to increased economic activity.

The state of economic life in Transoxiana during the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries is examined on a solid scholarly basis in the studies of G. Boboyorov. He evaluates trade, handicrafts, and the landownership system as the main forms of entrepreneurial activity and demonstrates the strengthening of economic ties between urban and rural economies. In these processes, the intensification of market relations in Samarkand, Bukhara, and other major cities played a significant role.

The fundamental research conducted by V. V. Bartold on the history of Turkestan provides an opportunity to analyze economic relations of the Timurid period from a historical and geographical perspective. In his works, the development of trade routes, urban infrastructure, and international economic relations is assessed as a key factor in entrepreneurial activity. In particular, trade conducted along the Great Silk Road enhanced regional and interregional economic integration.

The personality of Mirzo Ulug'bek and his era are comprehensively examined in the studies of N. Ibrohimov, who places special emphasis on Ulug'bek's approach to state governance, economic policy, and science-based decision-making. During Ulug'bek's reign, the establishment of a stable political environment enabled the development of trade and handicrafts and facilitated the expansion of entrepreneurial initiatives.

Issues related to medieval trade routes in Central Asia are analyzed in detail in the works of T. Mahmudov and O. Sayfiddinov. Their studies identify internal and external trade relations, caravan routes, customs duties, and market activities as the main drivers of economic development. These factors stimulated the activities of entrepreneurial entities during the period of Mirzo Ulug'bek.

The close interconnection between cultural and economic life in the Timurid period is highlighted in the research of M. Qodirov, who substantiates that developments in handicrafts, construction, and the arts were closely linked to economic activity. In addition, A. Yakubov evaluates Samarkand as a major economic and cultural center in the medieval period, demonstrating that the development of urban infrastructure strengthened the entrepreneurial environment.

The work *Zafarnama* by Nizam al-Din Shami is an important historical source illuminating the political and economic processes of the Timurid era, containing valuable information on trade, finance, and handicraft activities. Although Mirzo Ulug'bek's *Zij-i Jadid-i Koragoni* is not directly devoted to economic processes, it demonstrates the influence of scientific thinking and an approach based on precise calculation on societal development.

In general, the reviewed literature indicates that entrepreneurship during the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek developed on the basis of trade, handicrafts, and international economic relations. Political stability, attention to science and culture, and the presence of a favorable trade environment created the foundation for the growth of entrepreneurial activity during this period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article employs historical-analytical, comparative, and source-study methods. The research analyzes medieval historical sources as well as scholarly works by contemporary historians and economists.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Mirzo Ulug'bek, whose original name was Muhammad Taraghay (1394–1449), was the grandson of Amir Timur. As one of the most prominent representatives of the Timurid dynasty, his name occupies a distinguished place in world history as a major statesman and an outstanding astronomer and mathematician.

Despite the fact that his principal activities were closely associated with science, the period of Ulug'bek's rule was marked by notable progress in economic life, particularly in entrepreneurship, craftsmanship, and trade.

It may be stated, without exaggeration, that the formation of Mirzo Ulug'bek as a historical figure was strongly influenced by his grandfather Amir Timur, who possessed a powerful entrepreneurial and strategic-economic mindset. This approach directly shaped Ulug'bek's worldview. Amir Timur was among those rulers who, even in his own time, placed special emphasis on human capital.

If Amir Timur laid the foundations of the economy, Ulug'bek strengthened it through science.

Ulug'bek did not personally engage in entrepreneurial activity. However, he regarded economic stability and the welfare of the population as key priorities of state policy. For this reason, he paid particular attention to creating favorable conditions for merchants, craftsmen, and the business community. The tax system was organized in a relatively rational manner, and excessive fiscal pressure was reduced. This contributed to the development of free trade relations and to the activation of both domestic and foreign markets. As a result, free trade expanded. Notably, Ulug'bek consistently emphasized to his ministers the necessity of providing merchants with broad opportunities for activity.

Transoxiana was geographically located along the Great Silk Road, and during Ulug'bek's reign this advantage was used effectively. Between 1417 and 1430, major construction projects were carried out in Samarkand, particularly in the Registan square, including a grand madrasa, a khanqah, a muqatta' mosque, and a bathhouse. In addition, madrasas were built in Bukhara in 1417 and in Gijduvan in 1433. These structures contributed significantly to the socio-economic development of the cities. Major urban centers such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Gijduvan, and Shahrisabz became important hubs of regional and international trade.

Furthermore, Ulug'bek commissioned the construction of numerous public facilities, including caravanserais, trading domes (tims), chorsu markets, and bathhouses. The largest caravanserai, known as Mirzoyi, was located in the Registan area on the site of the present-day Tilla-Kari Madrasa. Such caravanserais and bathhouses were built not only in Samarkand but also in other major cities and along key trade routes. The construction of caravanserais, tims, and chorsu markets significantly facilitated commercial activity by ensuring the effective functioning of market-oriented infrastructure of that era. In other words, Ulug'bek made a substantial contribution to the development of urban infrastructure in the central cities of the state.

During Ulug'bek's reign, the development of public infrastructure also served as an important factor for entrepreneurship. Bathhouses, mosques, and rest facilities for travelers built in cities and along trade routes stimulated economic activity. These structures not only met the needs of the population but also demonstrated the economic strength and stability of the state.

Ulug'bek devoted considerable attention to architecture and construction. The Ulug'bek Madrasa in Samarkand, built between 1417 and 1430, was not only an educational institution but also an integral part of the city's economic life, as markets, craft workshops, and commercial shops operated in its vicinity.

The sultan, who ruled Transoxiana for forty years, devoted himself wholeheartedly to the advancement of science and did not spare the state treasury in pursuing this goal. During his reign, Samarkand became one of the most flourishing cultural centers of the East.

In our view, astronomical research during the time of Mirzo Ulug'bek required substantial financial resources. For example, the construction of the observatory involved building materials, astronomical instruments, and skilled labor, all of which were provided through entrepreneurial entities. The arrival of foreign scholars contributed to the development of the service sector. Housing, food, paper, ink, and scientific instruments were required for scholars and students. Such demands created new economic opportunities for merchants, farmers, and craftsmen.

Thus, the development of science expanded both production and service markets. The arrival of foreign scholars in Transoxiana during the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek was not accidental, but rather the result of a strong synergy between entrepreneurship, economic stability, and scientific advancement. Consequently, just as science was strongly supported during Ulug'bek's rule, entrepreneurship was also promoted at the level of state policy.

Craftsmanship was one of the most highly developed sectors of entrepreneurship during the reign of Ulug'bek. Artisans supplied their products not only to local markets but also to external ones. Pottery, jewelry making, blacksmithing, textile production, wood and metal carving, and architectural decorative arts experienced significant growth. In particular, the multicolored tiles, ornamental patterns, and inscriptions used in architectural decoration were the result of the work of highly skilled masters. Architectural art, in general, reached a particularly high level of development. For example, during the years 1434–1435, the main gate of the Shah-i Zinda complex was reconstructed and adorned with multicolored tiles, which stands as a vivid testament to the architectural achievements of Ulug'bek's era.

During the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek, foreign trade relations were highly developed. Continuous trade connections were maintained with China, India, Iran, Asia, and Europe. Under Ulug'bek's rule, the export of silk, spices, precious stones, paper, and metal goods was well organized, bringing substantial revenue to the state treasury.

In our view, Mirzo Ulug'bek significantly elevated Samarkand's status as an international trade center. More precisely, his efforts reveal the emergence and expansion of entrepreneurship in the country on an international scale.

The close interconnection between science and the economy is clearly evident in Ulug'bek's policies. He treated scholars with great respect and provided them with material support, which contributed to the development of disciplines such as astronomy, mathematics, and geography. Scientific progress, in turn, ensured greater precision in construction, engineering, and accounting practices, thereby exerting a positive influence on entrepreneurial activity.

The outcomes of scientific advancement directly served entrepreneurial needs. It should be particularly noted that the development of astronomical and mathematical knowledge required extensive measurement practices. For instance, accurate measurement was essential in construction, precise calculation in trade, and the application of geometry in land surveying. To meet these needs, various levels of specialized services were introduced and applied in practice. Such knowledge-intensive services enhanced the efficiency of entrepreneurial activity.

Thus, during Ulug'bek's era, entrepreneurship flourished especially in the fields of architecture, craftsmanship, and commerce. Secular sciences were studied on an exceptionally broad and intensive scale.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, entrepreneurship during the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek developed in close harmony with state policy. Trade, craftsmanship, and architecture served as the main pillars of economic life. The environment of peace, stability, and scientific orientation created by Ulug'bek transformed Transoxiana into one of the most developed and prosperous regions of the East at that time. This legacy continues to hold significant value today as an important historical experience for shaping national economic thinking and entrepreneurial culture.

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